

Master's Thesis

Learning Feature Fields for Efficient Object Search

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Abstract

Object search in previously unseen indoor environments requires an agent to reason about where target objects are likely to reside, even before they are visible. Humans exploit statistical regularities in how objects co-occur spatially, but endowing robotic agents with such priors in a general, open-vocabulary manner remains an open challenge. Existing approaches either rely on discrete object categories that limit generalization, or on vision-language similarity that can only reason about what is currently visible. We present Probabilistic Relative Feature Fields (ProReFF), a self-supervised method that learns spatial co-occurrence structure directly from visual feature embeddings, without requiring object labels or annotations. Given a query embedding and a spatial offset, ProReFF predicts the distribution of DINOv2 features likely to appear at that relative location. A key challenge in training is the inherent viewpoint ambiguity of relative spatial data: observing the same scene from different positions produces contradictory training signal. We address this with a learned alignment network that resolves these contradictions by predicting a canonical rotation for each training triplet. Building on ProReFF, we present an object search agent that queries the trained field at multiple spatial scales to identify scene regions whose semantic content best matches the predicted feature neighborhood around a target object. We evaluate on 100 object search challenges across 20 unseen buildings from the Matterport3D dataset, comparing against frontier-based methods and human participants. The proposed agent is 20% more efficient than the strongest baseline and achieves up to 80% of human performance.

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1 Introduction

One of the fundamental challenges for household robots is localising objects in previously unseen environments. Humans possess strong priors about the structure of domestic spaces. Even in an unfamiliar home, one naturally heads to the kitchen to look for a cup rather than the bathroom, and is more likely to find the missing TV remote on the sofa than on the kitchen countertop. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as *object co-occurrence*: certain objects tend to appear together or in characteristic spatial contexts. Because these regularities enable humans to search efficiently, robotic agents should also be able to exploit such priors when exploring new environments.

The problem of navigating to a target object in an unknown environment, commonly called *ObjectNav* [?], has become a central benchmark task for embodied intelligence. In this task, an agent must navigate through a previously unseen environment to locate an object specified by name (e.g., “chair” or “microwave”). A naïve strategy for solving this problem is to explore the environment exhaustively using classical exploration methods such as *frontier exploration* [?], which guides a robot toward the boundary between explored and unexplored space. While such strategies ensure eventual coverage of the environment, they do not leverage semantic information about where objects are likely to be located. Efficient object search instead requires the agent to reason about *where* target objects are likely to reside relative to the surrounding scene, even when the target is not yet visible. Humans naturally rely on statistical regularities in how objects and rooms are arranged within homes, priors

that are acquired implicitly through years of experience. We depict an example of the *ObjectNav* task in ??.

Early work in robotics has attempted to model such priors explicitly by learning object–object or object–scene relationships from annotated datasets or internet-scale data [?, ?, ?]. Given these priors, an agent can prioritise exploration of regions where the target object is more likely to appear. However, these classical approaches typically represent objects using discrete categorical labels encoded as one-hot vectors. While effective within the vocabulary of objects seen during training, they face an inherent transfer barrier: introducing new object categories requires additional annotations and retraining of the model.

Recent progress in Large Language Models (LLMs) has provided an alternative source of prior knowledge. Because LLMs are trained on large corpora of internet text, they capture a vast amount of commonsense knowledge about everyday environments. Several recent approaches leverage this knowledge to guide robotic exploration by constructing *scene graphs*, structured representations that describe objects in the environment and their spatial relationships [?, ?, ?, ?]. In these systems, candidate objects or regions are first detected from the robot’s observations and inserted into the scene graph, after which an LLM reasons over the graph to suggest promising exploration directions. For example, ESC [?] uses GLIP [?] with predefined object and room prompts to obtain labeled regions from the current observation and construct a semantic map. These labels are fed to an LLM, which scores frontiers based on commonsense object and room relationships. More broadly, a growing family of scene-graph-based approaches combines hierarchical spatial representations with LLM reasoning to enable open-vocabulary navigation.

Despite their flexibility, these approaches remain fundamentally tied to discrete object instances. They rely on an object detector or segmentation model to first propose candidates whose labels can be passed to the LLM. As a result, their performance is constrained by the quality and vocabulary of the perception module, regardless of

Figure 1: An example of the ObjectNav task. A robot is tasked with finding a pot in an unknown environment, starting in a bedroom ($T = 0$), and has to choose a frontier for exploration. In this case the robot chooses the bathroom ($T = 1$) and does not find the object there. It then navigates to the corridor and chooses the left side frontier ($T = 3$). Finally the robot successfully finds the pot ($T = 5$). In this case the navigation was inefficient because the robot didn't exploit priors on objects co-occurrences.

the richness of the LLM’s knowledge. Furthermore, building and maintaining scene graphs during exploration introduces additional computational complexity.

An alternative line of work has recently emerged that relies on *vision–language representations*. Modern vision–language models such as CLIP [?] are trained on large datasets of paired images and text captions, allowing them to embed both visual inputs and language queries into a shared semantic space. In this embedding space, images and text describing similar concepts are mapped to nearby vectors. These representations can therefore be used to perform open-vocabulary recognition without task-specific training.

Several navigation methods exploit these embeddings by comparing the semantic similarity between the current observation and the target object description. For example, VLFM [?] and OneMap [?] construct language-grounded value maps from RGB observations and score candidate exploration frontiers according to their similarity to the embedding of the target text prompt. Because these approaches operate directly in a continuous embedding space, they can generalise to objects that were never explicitly labelled in the training data. Moreover, their scoring functions are computationally lightweight and do not require additional annotated datasets. However, these similarity-based methods rely solely on information that is currently visible to the agent. When the surrounding context does not contain features semantically similar to the target object, the signal used to guide exploration becomes weak. In such cases the agent has no mechanism to reason about what might lie *beyond* the current frontier based on typical spatial relationships between objects.

Recent work on neural feature fields provides a promising direction for representing semantic information in three-dimensional environments. Inspired by neural radiance fields [?], these methods learn continuous functions that map spatial locations to high-dimensional feature representations. Prior work has demonstrated that vision–language embeddings can be encoded in such fields, enabling robots to query reconstructed scenes using natural language [?,?,?]. Systems such as CLIP-Fields [?]

and ConceptFusion [?] fuse pixel-aligned semantic features extracted from foundation models into dense 3D maps using standard SLAM pipelines. These representations enable open-set scene querying and language-guided manipulation without additional training.

Nevertheless, existing feature fields are typically fitted to a single scene and therefore capture only the semantics of that specific environment. In other words, they describe *what is present in the current scene*, but not *what tends to appear near what* across different environments. Consequently, they cannot encode the statistical spatial priors that are essential for efficient object search.

Neural feature fields naturally enable encoding spatial co-occurrence priors in continuous space. Unlike scene graphs, which require discrete object proposals and named categories, or LLMs, which reason over symbolic representations, feature fields operate directly in a continuous spatial and semantic space, precisely the setting in which vision-language embeddings live. The feature field trained across many environments will reflect statistical regularities about how features tend to co-occur across space.

In this work, we address the problem of estimating object co-occurrences in a self-supervised manner in the continuous embedding space of Visual Language Models (VLMs). We propose *Probabilistic Relative Feature Fields* (ProReFF), a representation that models the spatial co-occurrence structure of vision-language embeddings across environments. Instead of learning explicit object relations or querying for specific categories, our approach learns these relationships directly from the co-occurrences of visual features. Given a semantic feature query and spatial offsets relative to it, ProReFF predicts the distribution of features likely to appear at those locations. This allows a navigating agent to ask not *“is the target here?”* but rather *“does what I currently observe tend to co-occur with the target?”*.

We further present an exploration strategy that uses ProReFF to reason about the probable spatial context of a target object and guide exploration toward semantically

promising regions. Crucially, this strategy requires no object proposals and no scene-specific fitting: the feature field is trained once on a collection of real-world 3D indoor-environments and then deployed zero-shot in unseen scenes.

We evaluate our approach on the Matterport3D dataset [?], comparing it against simple baselines, zero-shot object search agents as well as human participants. Our results demonstrate that ProReFF improves search efficiency, particularly in challenging multi-floor environments where simple similarity-based methods struggle.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first feature field designed to encode cross-environment spatial priors for object navigation. Our specific contributions are:

- ProReFF: a probabilistic feature field that models the spatial co-occurrence structure of vision-language embeddings across environments and is trained in a fully self-supervised manner without semantic labels.
- An object search strategy guided by ProReFF that leverages spatial semantic context at multiple scales.
- An evaluation on Matterport3D comparing our method with other zero-shot object search agents and human participants.

The thesis is structured as follows. ?? covers the core mathematical concepts used in the Approach and Evaluation chapters. ?? reviews related work on object navigation, vision-language representations, and neural feature fields. ?? introduces ProReFF, presenting the full method from the probabilistic field formulation to the object search agent. ?? describes the dataset, simulator, and data processing pipeline used for training, as well as the platform used for the human baseline. ?? presents the experimental evaluation, assessing the predictive quality of ProReFF and its performance as a navigation agent against baselines and human participants. ?? summarizes the findings, and ?? concludes the thesis and outlines directions for future work.

2 Background

2.1 Preliminaries

We denote by \mathbb{R}^E the E -dimensional real vector space. Throughout this thesis, $E = 768$ corresponds to the dimensionality of DINOv2 [?] patch embeddings. Feature embeddings are represented as vectors $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^E$ and spatial positions as vectors $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$.

L2-Normalization. Given a vector $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^E$, its L2-normalized form is $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{q}/\|\mathbf{q}\|_2$, where $\|\mathbf{q}\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^E q_i^2}$ is the Euclidean norm. L2-normalized vectors lie on the unit hypersphere \mathcal{S}^{E-1} , and their pairwise dot product equals their cosine similarity:

$$\cos(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}') = \frac{\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{q}'}{\|\mathbf{q}\|_2 \|\mathbf{q}'\|_2}.$$

Cosine similarity takes values in $[-1, 1]$, with 1 indicating identical directions and -1 indicating opposite directions. Throughout the thesis we only work with L2-normalized embeddings and denote them simply with \mathbf{q} .

Rodrigues' Rotation Formula. Given a rotation vector $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and a vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, Rodrigues' formula computes the rotation of \mathbf{v} by angle $\theta = \|\mathbf{r}\|$ around unit axis $\hat{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{r}/\|\mathbf{r}\|$:

$$R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{v} \cos \|\mathbf{r}\| + (\hat{\mathbf{r}} \times \mathbf{v}) \sin \|\mathbf{r}\| + \hat{\mathbf{r}}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}^\top \mathbf{v})(1 - \cos \|\mathbf{r}\|), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{r}/\|\mathbf{r}\|$ is the normalized rotation axis. The formula decomposes the rotated vector into three components: the projection of \mathbf{v} along the rotation axis, which is unchanged; the component perpendicular to the axis rotated in the plane; and a correction term. This provides a compact, differentiable parameterization of 3D rotations using only a three-dimensional vector $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, making it well suited for use as the output of a neural network. We use R as the alignment operator in the Alignment Network g defined in ??.

K-Means Clustering. Given a set of vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_i\}_{i=1}^N \subset \mathbb{R}^E$ and a number of clusters K , K-means finds a partition $\{C_1, \dots, C_K\}$ of $\{1, \dots, N\}$ and corresponding centroids $\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_k\}_{k=1}^K \subset \mathbb{R}^E$ by minimizing the total within-cluster variance:

$$\min_{\{C_k\}, \{\boldsymbol{\mu}_k\}} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i \in C_k} d(\mathbf{e}_i, \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)^2, \quad \boldsymbol{\mu}_k = \frac{\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_k}{\|\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_k\|_2}, \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_k = \frac{1}{|C_k|} \sum_{i \in C_k} \mathbf{e}_i, \quad (2)$$

where $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a distance function. In this work, since all embeddings are L2-normalized and lie on \mathcal{S}^{E-1} , we use the Euclidean distance $d(\mathbf{e}_i, \boldsymbol{\mu}_k) = \|\mathbf{e}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k\|_2$. For unit vectors, Euclidean distance is monotonically equivalent to angular distance, since $\|\mathbf{e}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k\|^2 = 2(1 - \mathbf{e}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\mu}_k) = 2(1 - \cos \theta)$, so minimizing Euclidean distance yields the same cluster assignments as minimizing $\cos^{-1}(\mathbf{e}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)$. Once clustering has converged, each centroid $\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_k$ is projected back onto \mathcal{S}^{E-1} via L2-normalization. We use K-means to cluster predicted and observed feature embeddings in the search agent (??) and to evaluate the predictive quality of ProReFF (??).

Hungarian Algorithm. Given two sets of clusters $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, \dots, c_K\}$ and $\mathcal{C}' = \{c'_1, \dots, c'_K\}$, the Hungarian algorithm finds the optimal one-to-one assignment π^* between clusters that minimizes total assignment cost:

$$\pi^* = \arg \min_{\pi \in \Pi_K} \sum_{k=1}^K d(c_k, c'_{\pi(k)}),$$

where Π_K is the set of all permutations of $\{1, \dots, K\}$ and d is a cost function between clusters. Specifically, we compute d as the cosine distance between cluster centroids, $d(\boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \boldsymbol{\mu}'_{\pi(k)}) = 1 - \cos(\boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \boldsymbol{\mu}'_{\pi(k)})$. We use the Hungarian algorithm to find the optimal correspondence between predicted and ground truth cluster centroids when evaluating ProReFF (??) and when computing the Angular Wasserstein distance (??).

Wasserstein Distance. The Wasserstein distance measures the dissimilarity between two probability distributions by computing the minimum cost of transporting mass from one distribution to the other. For two univariate Gaussian distributions $p = \mathcal{N}(\mu_1, \sigma_1^2)$ and $q = \mathcal{N}(\mu_2, \sigma_2^2)$, the 2-Wasserstein distance has a closed-form expression:

$$W_2(p, q) = \sqrt{(\mu_1 - \mu_2)^2 + (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2}. \quad (3)$$

This decomposes naturally into a term penalizing differences in location and a term penalizing differences in spread, which motivates our adaptation to the space of L2-normalized embeddings. In our work, we replace the Euclidean distance between means with angular distance, and the difference of standard deviations is computed in angular space. Each distribution is represented by a set of K clusters with centroids and angular spreads, and optimal cluster correspondences are found via the Hungarian algorithm. The full definition of our distance metric is given in ??.

Model Functions. We introduce two learned functions used throughout the Approach chapter. The *relative feature field* f_θ , parameterized by weights θ , maps a query embedding and a spatial displacement to a predicted feature distribution:

$$f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^E \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^E \times \mathbb{R}_{>0}, \quad f_\theta(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}) = (\boldsymbol{\mu}, \sigma^2), \quad (4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu} \in \mathcal{S}^{E-1}$ is the predicted mean embedding and $\sigma^2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the predicted variance. The *alignment network* g_ϕ , parameterized by weights ϕ , observes a full

training triplet and outputs a rotation vector in $\mathfrak{se}(3)$:

$$g_\phi : \mathbb{R}^E \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3, \quad g_\phi(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q}') = \mathbf{r}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ encodes a rotation via Rodrigues' formula, i.e. the aligned displacement is $R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v})$.

3 Related Work

This chapter surveys the work most relevant to ProReFF. We first review methods for object search and co-occurrence reasoning ([?]), then discuss visual representations used in robotic perception ([?]), and finally cover neural feature fields and semantic scene representations ([?]).

3.1 Object Search & Co-Occurrences

In *ObjectNav*, an agent is tasked with finding an object of a target category in unseen environments [?]. A central challenge is deciding which *frontiers* to explore next, where frontiers denote the boundaries between explored and unexplored space [?]. This requires a scoring function that can reason about where the target is likely to be, and such functions typically build on the idea of *object co-occurrences*, *i.e.*, that cups are more likely to be found near a fridge than in a garage. Classically, such co-occurrences have been obtained from annotated datasets or mined from internet data and integrated into probabilistic planners [?, ?, ?, ?].

Kollar and Roy [?] provide a concrete instantiation of this idea: co-occurrence statistics mined from Flickr image captions are used to construct compatibility matrices between object and scene categories, which are then queried to produce a likelihood map over possible object locations given detections already registered in the environment. This likelihood map is used to plan paths that minimise expected travel distance to the target. Zeng [?] extended this direction with Semantic Linking Maps

(SLiM), which jointly maintain a probabilistic belief over both target and landmark object locations, and model inter-object spatial relations at a finer granularity, distinguishing relations such as *on*, *in*, and *proximity*, to guide an active search strategy. Both approaches share a fundamental assumption with the broader classical co-occurrence literature: that object identity is available, either through annotated maps or trained detectors. Our approach removes this requirement by operating entirely in the space of visual features, learning spatial co-occurrence structure without relying on object labels or category annotations.

Another approach for tackling ObjectNav is to frame it as a reinforcement learning problem. DD-PPO [?] demonstrated that distributed deep reinforcement learning at scale, can train agents capable of navigating to target objects in photorealistic environments without any hand-crafted priors. SemExp [?] extended this by combining learned exploration with explicit semantic maps: the agent builds a top-down map recording the presence of different object categories as one-hot vectors, and a learned high-level policy selects which regions of the map to explore. While these approaches demonstrated the viability of end-to-end and modular learning for ObjectNav, they remain bound to a fixed set of object categories and require large amounts of interaction data to train.

These methods were largely developed and evaluated on dedicated embodied AI simulation platforms. Habitat [?] provides a framework for training and evaluating embodied agents across a range of photorealistic 3D environments, while AI2-THOR [?] offers interactive indoor environments with physics simulation, enabling the study of manipulation alongside navigation. More recently, HM3D [?] introduced a large-scale dataset of high-fidelity 3D scans specifically designed for embodied navigation benchmarks. In this work, we evaluate on the Matterport3D simulator [?], which provides photorealistic RGB-D panoramic imagery from real indoor environments, offering high visual fidelity that makes it particularly suitable for evaluating vision-based agents.

The recent rise of Vision-Language Models (VLMs) has enabled a new class of approaches capable of open-vocabulary zero-shot navigation. CLIP [?] demonstrated that contrastive training on large-scale image-text pairs yields a joint embedding space in which images and natural language descriptions of the same concept are mapped to similar representations, enabling zero-shot object localisation without any task-specific training. The simplest instantiation of this idea is CoW [?], which combines CLIP-based object localisation with classical frontier-based exploration. As the agent explores, it builds a top-down 2D occupancy map from depth observations and pose estimates. At each step, object relevance is computed directly from the current RGB observation: either by computing the similarity between CLIP patch embeddings and the target text embedding, or by extracting a pixel-level relevance map via gradient-based attention through the CLIP ViT backbone [?]. These relevance scores are back-projected into the top-down map using the depth image, accumulating the maximum relevance per map cell. If no confident localisation is available, the agent navigates greedily to the closest unexplored frontier; once the accumulated relevance in the map exceeds a threshold, it plans directly to the highest-relevance cell and stops. Despite requiring no task-specific training, CoW achieves competitive performance with methods trained for hundreds of millions of steps, demonstrating the surprising effectiveness of vision-language embeddings for open-vocabulary object search. More sophisticated approaches extend this by maintaining richer semantic map representations. VLFM [?] replaces binary frontier scoring with a continuously updated value map: at each step, a vision-language model (BLIP-2 [?]) computes a cosine similarity score between the current RGB observation and a text prompt encoding the target (e.g., "*Seems like there is a {target} ahead.*"), and this score is projected onto a top-down 2D map weighted by viewing confidence. The frontier with the highest accumulated value is selected for exploration. OneMap [?] takes this a step further by storing raw CLIP feature embeddings at each map location rather than pre-computed similarity scores. This makes the map target-agnostic and reusable across queries, enabling multi-object navigation without rebuilding the

representation.

While VLM-based approaches score frontiers by direct visual similarity to the target, a complementary strategy is to exploit the commonsense knowledge encoded in Large Language Models (LLMs) to reason about where objects are likely to be found. ESC [?] improves on CoW by constraining exploration using candidate prompts scored by an LLM: a grounded detector, GLIP [?], first proposes named regions from the current observation, whose labels are then passed to an LLM which uses them to score the frontiers. In order to expose larger spaces for reasoning and not rely on the quality of a dense map, scene graphs can be built as a robotic agent progresses through an environment [?, ?]. Coupled with LLMs, such scene graph representations can be used to perform effective navigation in an open-vocabulary setting by using the LLM to score graph nodes for exploration [?, ?, ?, ?].

Our approach similarly builds on the advantages of VLMs but seeks to remove reliance on explicit object labels. While LLM-based approaches are open-vocabulary, they require object proposals and names to function. Although this is not the case for VLM frontier-based approaches such as OneMap, they have the inherent limitation of generating frontier scores that can be uninformative when the agent cannot yet see anything semantically related to the target. By training a relative feature field, we aim to expand the region of semantically related concepts. This enables an agent to reason not only about what is currently similar to the target object, but also about what tends to co-occur with it spatially, without requiring object candidates or training labels.

3.2 Visual Representations for Robotics

The emergence of self-supervised visual representation learning has produced a family of models whose features have proven broadly useful for robotic perception tasks.

Figure 2: Visualization of the first three PCA components of DINOv2 patch features, taken from [?]. Each component is mapped to a colour channel and computed jointly across images in the same column. Semantically corresponding parts are consistently matched across changes in pose, style, and object instance, while background regions are suppressed by thresholding the first PCA component.

CLIP [?] trains a vision encoder and a text encoder jointly using a contrastive objective on hundreds of millions of image-text pairs scraped from the internet, yielding a shared embedding space with strong zero-shot transfer properties. The resulting image features capture high-level semantic content and align naturally with language, making them a popular choice for open-vocabulary navigation and manipulation tasks.

A parallel line of work has focused on self-supervised training of Vision Transformers (ViTs) [?] without language supervision. DINO [?] introduced a self-distillation objective in which a student network is trained to match the output of a momentum-updated teacher network across differently augmented views of the same image. Despite the absence of explicit semantic supervision, DINO features were found to exhibit strong emergent properties: the self-attention maps of DINO-trained ViTs spontaneously segment semantically meaningful regions, suggesting that the model implicitly learns object-level structure from unlabelled images.

DINOv2 [?] extended this approach with a larger curated dataset, improved training

recipes, and increased model capacity, producing patch-level features with significantly stronger spatial and semantic properties. As shown in ??, taken from the original paper [?], the patch features learned by DINOv2 exhibit strong semantic consistency: corresponding parts of different object instances, such as wings across bird species or wheels across vehicle types, are mapped to similar feature vectors, even under large changes in pose, style, or viewpoint. Amir [?] empirically demonstrated that these features encode well-localized semantic information at fine spatial granularity, making them particularly suitable for dense prediction tasks. A subsequent analysis [?] identified artefacts in the attention maps of ViTs trained with DINO, attributing them to the presence of uninformative background tokens. The introduction of *register tokens*, additional learned tokens that absorb global information, was shown to resolve these artefacts, producing cleaner attention maps and more uniformly informative patch features. We build our approach on DINOv2 features, which provide the dense spatial-semantic representations required for constructing meaningful feature point clouds.

While DINOv2 itself does not provide a language encoder, Talk2DINO [?] provides a learned mapping from CLIP language embeddings to the DINOv2 feature space, trained on top of DINOv2 with registers. This enables fine-grained language-based queries on DINOv2 features, overcoming the coarser region-level language grounding of previous approaches [?], and allowing our agent to specify target objects using natural language while reasoning in the richer DINOv2 feature space.

3.3 Feature Fields & Semantic Scene Representations

Neural fields are trained functions that predict values given 3D coordinates and additional optional queries. Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [?] established the paradigm: a multilayer perceptron is fitted to a set of RGB-D observations via differentiable volume rendering, predicting density and radiance at arbitrary 3D coordinates and

Figure 3: Comparison of 2D CLIP and LERF relevancy maps for the same text queries, taken from the original paper [?]. The left column shows similarity maps interpolated over patchwise 2D CLIP embeddings; the right column shows the corresponding maps rendered from LERF. By incorporating information from multiple views through volumetric language rendering, LERF produces relevancy activations that are more localised and better aligned with the underlying scene geometry.

enabling photorealistic novel view synthesis. The original formulation required per-scene optimization over many hours, but subsequent work such as Instant-NGP [?] dramatically reduced training time through hash-based feature grids. More recently, 3D Gaussian Splatting [?] proposed an alternative scene representation using explicit 3D Gaussians optimized via differentiable rasterization, achieving real-time rendering while maintaining high visual fidelity.

Beyond visual scene reproduction, several works have derived utility from neural fields by storing high-dimensional semantic features rather than RGB radiance.

LERF [?] embeds CLIP features within a NeRF by supervising the field with multi-scale CLIP patch embeddings, enabling open-vocabulary language queries that localize semantic concepts within a 3D scene. As shown in ??, because LERF aggregates CLIP embeddings across multiple views via volumetric rendering, its relevancy maps are more spatially precise and better aligned with scene geometry than those obtained from flat 2D CLIP features.

Distilled Feature Fields [?] similarly distill vision-language features into neural fields for language-guided robotic manipulation. Feature Splatting [?] and related approaches extend this idea to 3D Gaussian Splatting, combining the rendering efficiency of explicit Gaussians with the open-vocabulary querying capability of embedded semantic features.

A complementary approach to per-scene feature fields is the fusion of semantic features into explicit 3D maps. CLIP-Fields [?] and ConceptFusion [?] show that pixel-aligned semantic features from foundation models can be fused into dense 3D maps via standard SLAM pipelines, enabling open-set multimodal scene querying without additional training. These instance-specific representations, however, are fitted to a single scene and encode no statistical regularities across environments, they describe *what is here*, not *what tends to appear near what*.

A related but distinct problem is 3D scene completion, where the goal is to predict unobserved geometry or semantics from partial observations of the current scene. Recent approaches such as [?] perform direct scene completion by predicting features at unobserved locations conditioned on the current view. While such methods extend perception beyond the immediately visible, they remain tied to the specific scene being observed and do not encode priors that generalise across environments.

In this work, we fit a probabilistic neural field in an unsupervised manner on feature point clouds generated from RGB-D observations. Unlike the instance-specific fields described above, we do not seek to reconstruct a specific scene but to obtain a field that encodes a general notion of how features relate spatially across environments.

This cross-environment generalisation distinguishes our approach from both scene-specific feature fields and scene completion methods, and is what enables our agent to reason about likely object locations in entirely unseen buildings without any scene-specific fitting.

4 Approach

Our approach is based on the observation that the spatial distribution of visual features in indoor environments is not random: objects that share functional or semantic relationships tend to appear in consistent spatial configurations across different buildings and scenes. We aim to capture this structure in a learned probabilistic field that, given a query feature embedding and a displacement vector, predicts what kinds of features are likely to be found at that relative location. This field is trained in a self-supervised manner from RGB-D observations, requiring no object labels or category annotations. First, we define the *Relative Feature Field* model (??), a neural field that maps a query embedding and a displacement vector to a predicted feature distribution. Second, because the training data is inherently ambiguous due to view-point variation, we introduce an *Alignment Network* (??) that learns to decompose each training triple into a canonical orientation, resolving contradictions that would otherwise prevent the field from learning consistent spatial structure. Finally, we describe the *Search Agent* (??), which uses the trained field at test time to score and select navigation targets by matching the predicted feature neighborhoods against the agent’s accumulated observations of the current scene.

4.1 Relative Feature Field Model

The aim of our method is to predict the spatially relative occurrence of deep feature embeddings. Given, for example, a feature stemming from a stove, we aim for our

model to capture the possibility of a pot being found near the stove. Additionally, a bit farther away, the model should be able to indicate the presence of a fridge or a sink. To achieve this goal, we assume to be given a query feature $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^E$ (where $E = 768$) and a displacement vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ for which our model predicts a mean feature $\boldsymbol{\mu} \in \mathbb{R}^E$ and a scalar variance $\sigma^2 \in \mathbb{R}$ representing the predicted spread of features around $\boldsymbol{\mu}$. Our full model is thus a map

$$f : \mathbb{R}^E \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^E \times \mathbb{R}_{>0}.$$

We implement f as an MLP with 8 layers each of which has 256 hidden units, following the architecture of NeRF [?], which demonstrated that MLPs are well suited to fitting continuous functions over spatial inputs. We adopt the same skip connection design, which concatenates the inputs to the fifth layer to help the network retain input information at greater depth. Unlike NeRF, we do not apply positional encoding, as this encoding is designed to produce sharp high-frequency outputs, which is appropriate for novel view synthesis but contrary to our goal of learning smooth, general spatial trends across environments. In order to train this model, we require training triplets $(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q}')$ consisting of a query embedding, a displacement vector, and a target embedding, whose construction is described in ???. As our model is meant to predict distributions, we train f_θ by minimizing a cosine-based negative log-likelihood loss over all training pairs in \mathcal{D} :

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}|} \sum_{(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q}') \in \mathcal{D}} \frac{(1 - \cos(\mathbf{q}', \boldsymbol{\mu}))^2}{2\sigma^2} + \frac{1}{2} \log \sigma^2, \quad (6)$$

where $(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \sigma^2) = f_\theta(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v})$ and $\cos(\mathbf{q}', \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \mathbf{q}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the cosine similarity between the target and predicted embeddings, since \mathbf{q}' are L2-normalized and $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is L2-normalized by computing $\boldsymbol{\mu} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\mu} / \|\boldsymbol{\mu}\|_2$ on the output of the MLP before it is returned.

Figure 4: Depiction of the ambiguity problem in the data. Observing the same query feature (red dot), from two different locations can lead to contradictory target features (pink dot) given the same offset vector. In the schematic, we illustrate the effect of the learned alignment on this problem. In two separate observation instances, the alignment R rotates the observations such that the query contradiction is resolved.

4.2 Alignment Network

A fundamental challenge of our goal is that the training data can be highly ambiguous. Given that v is relative, and our model is not given some constant frame of reference, it is feasible to produce contradictory data points by observing the same scene from two different angles. As illustrated in ?? (top), for the same query (vase) and offset vector the model would be required to predict two different target embeddings: one encoding the countertop and one the book. As a remedy, one could curate or filter the dataset to avoid exhibiting the problem. However, this would

likely strongly bias the inference of the model towards an artificial data distribution. We propose an alternative approach: a learned dataset decomposition. During training, we introduce an auxiliary network g , which is allowed to observe the full training triple. Given such a triple, g outputs a rotation vector $\mathbf{r} \in \mathfrak{se}_3$ as

$$g : \mathbb{R}^E \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^E \rightarrow \mathfrak{se}_3.$$

Using the Rodrigues formula for rotation

$$\begin{aligned} R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) &= \mathbf{v} \cos \|\mathbf{r}\| + (\hat{\mathbf{r}} \times \mathbf{v}) \sin \|\mathbf{r}\| \\ &+ \hat{\mathbf{r}}(\hat{\mathbf{r}}^T \mathbf{v})(1 - \cos \|\mathbf{r}\|), \end{aligned}$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ being the normalized rotation vector \mathbf{r} , we augment the forward pass in our training case as

$$\hat{f}(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q}') = f(\mathbf{q}, R(g(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{q}'), \mathbf{v}), \mathbf{q}').$$

Concretely, two training triplets are contradictory when they share the same query embedding and offset vector yet differ in their target embedding. The alignment network resolves this by rotating the offset vector of each triple independently: triplets that were contradictory before alignment are mapped to distinct offset directions, so that the field f no longer needs to predict different targets for the same input, we picture this in ?? (bottom).

The resulting training architecture, combining f and g is depicted in ?? (Training). This formulation enables the model to learn a suitable data decomposition during training using only rotations. While this removes the ability to infer precise relative locations of objects, it preserves distances, which can be exploited for navigation tasks. We implement g as an MLP with 2 layers and 256 hidden units.

Figure 5: Overview of ProReFF. We train a relative feature field, which predicts a mean embedding and a variance, given a query embedding \mathbf{q} and a relative offset \mathbf{v} . This network is trained in an unsupervised manner from feature point cloud observations. To enable this training, we introduce a learned data alignment model. We demonstrate the utility of ProReFF for object search by using it to infer distributions of features around a target object. These distributions are compared with the agent’s current observations, and a choice is made between following the current observations or inferring further features.

4.3 Search Agent

The environment in which the agent operates is a discrete graph-based environment, where nodes correspond to navigable viewpoints connected by edges to their spatial neighbors. From each viewpoint, the agent obtains an RGB-D panoramic observation, from which DINOv2 patch embeddings are extracted and back-projected into

3D, obtaining a per-viewpoint point cloud. These are merged into a global semantic point cloud using the 3D poses provided by the simulator. The agent moves through the environment by selecting a target node and traversing the graph toward it. The description of the simulator and dataset used in our experiments is provided in ???. We define a navigation agent A tasked with finding a target object o in T discrete navigation steps, where a step consists of moving to a viewpoint in the environment’s connectivity graph. At each step, the agent maintains an accumulated semantic point cloud $\{(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{q}_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ where $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbf{q}_i \in \mathbb{R}^E$ are the 3D position and DINOv2 feature embedding of each observed point respectively. We define a target object o for which we obtain a text embedding $\mathbf{q}_o \in \mathbb{R}^E$ either directly using CLIP [?], or by mapping a CLIP embedding to the DINOv2 feature space using Talk2DINO [?]. The agent selects a target point $\mathbf{p}^* \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in the accumulated point cloud (among unvisited points) and navigates to the nearest viewpoint to \mathbf{p}^* in the connectivity graph. After navigating to a viewpoint, we mark it as *visited* together with all points within a radius of 1.5 meters.

The agent’s target selection strategy distinguishes between two cases: if a sufficiently similar feature is already visible in the accumulated point cloud, the agent exploits this observation by navigating directly toward it; otherwise, it falls back to querying ProReFF to reason about where co-occurring features are likely to be found. To select \mathbf{p}^* , first, the agent checks the similarity to the target:

$$s^* = \max_i \mathbf{q}_i^\top \mathbf{q}_o \quad (7)$$

We define an exploitation threshold τ , above which $s^* > \tau$ the agent follows the most similar point directly:

$$\mathbf{p}^* = \mathbf{p}_i : \arg \max_i \mathbf{q}_i^\top \mathbf{q}_o \quad (8)$$

Otherwise, the agent queries ProReFF with \mathbf{q}_o over a sphere \mathcal{S}_r of uniformly sampled points at radius r , obtaining predicted embeddings $\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_k\}_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{S}_r|}$ as depicted in ??

(Inference), via:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \sigma_k^2 = f_\theta(\mathbf{q}_o, \mathbf{s}_k), \quad \mathbf{s}_k \in \mathcal{S}_r \quad (9)$$

We cluster the predicted embeddings $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$ into K clusters using K -means, yielding the *field clustering* \mathcal{C}_F . The observed scene is then partitioned into spatial cells $\{\mathcal{X}_j\}$, and the embeddings within each cell are likewise clustered into K clusters, yielding a *scene clustering* \mathcal{C}_j per cell. We mark a cell as *visited* if at least 80% of its points are *visited*. The agent selects the unvisited cell \mathcal{X}_{j^*} whose scene clustering best matches the field clustering under the distance \mathcal{D} :

$$j^* = \arg \min_{j \in \text{unvisited}} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{C}_j, \mathcal{C}_F). \quad (10)$$

The distance \mathcal{D} is the Angular Wasserstein distance of the distributions, which we define in ???. Finally, among all unvisited points belonging to cell \mathcal{X}_{j^*} , the agent navigates to the point closest to its current position.

The scoring procedure above operates at a single spatial scale. To handle cases where no sufficiently good match is found at the current scale, we perform an incremental expansion of the spatial context. We define L radii $r_1 < r_2 < \dots < r_L$. For each level of context l , we perform field inference (??) using radius r_l , obtaining predicted embeddings over the corresponding sphere and clustering the predicted means into a field clustering \mathcal{C}_F^l . This yields a hierarchy of predicted fields encoding feature neighborhoods at progressively larger spatial scales.

At each navigation step t , the agent evaluates all levels and maintains a running best matching cost c_t^l for each level l , initialized as $c_0^l = \infty$ and updated as:

$$c_t^l = \min \left(c_{t-1}^l, \min_{j \in \text{unvisited}} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{C}_j, \mathcal{C}_F^l) \right). \quad (11)$$

At each step, the agent evaluates levels in order, committing to the first level l at

Figure 6: At each step, the agent clusters the predicted feature field embeddings (red circles) and the observed scene embeddings within each spatial cell (light blue squares), then selects the unvisited cell whose cluster distribution best matches the predicted field under the Angular Wasserstein distance (??).

which the current best match represents an improvement over the stored cost:

$$\ell^* = \min \left\{ l : \min_{j \in \text{unvisited}} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{C}_j, \mathcal{C}_F^l) \leq c_{t-1}^l + \epsilon \right\}, \quad (12)$$

where ϵ is a small tolerance. If no level satisfies this condition, the agent falls back to the cell with the lowest cost across all levels:

$$j^* = \arg \min_{j \in \text{unvisited}, l \in \{1, \dots, L\}} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{C}_j, \mathcal{C}_F^l). \quad (13)$$

We illustrate the high level comparison process in ??.

Together, the Relative Feature Field, the Alignment Network, and the Search Agent form a complete pipeline: features are predicted, training ambiguities are resolved, and the agent reasons about where co-occurring objects are likely to be found.

5 Datasets

This chapter describes the dataset and simulation environment used to train and evaluate ProReFF, the data generation procedure for constructing training triplets, and the human experiment platform used to establish a performance baseline.

5.1 Dataset and Simulator

Matterport3D [?] is a large-scale RGB-D dataset comprising 10,800 panoramic viewpoints across 90 building-scale indoor scenes, including homes, offices, and hotels. Each panoramic viewpoint provides 18 aligned color and depth images covering approximately the full sphere, at a resolution of 1280×1024 pixels, along with precise camera poses and global surface reconstructions. The diversity and building-scale coverage of Matterport3D make it particularly well suited for learning and evaluating agents that must reason about spatial structure across entire indoor environments. Sample images from the dataset are shown in ??.

We use the Matterport3D Simulator [?], an embodied AI platform built on top of the Matterport3D dataset, which enables agents to navigate indoor environments through a discrete graph-based action space. Each building is represented as a navigation graph in which nodes correspond to panoramic viewpoints and edges connect viewpoints that are mutually visible and within a navigable distance, with an average inter-viewpoint spacing of approximately 2.25m. At each node, the simulator provides the full panoramic RGB-D observation and the associated camera pose,

Figure 7: Images from the Matterport3D dataset, as depicted the dataset comprises a large variety of indoor environments.

allowing the agent to both perceive the scene and localize itself within the building. Navigation consists of discrete steps between connected viewpoints, abstracting away low-level motion planning and allowing research to focus on high-level spatial reasoning. Across the full dataset the navigation graphs contain an average of approximately 120 viewpoints per building making each episode a non-trivial search problem. We choose this simulator over alternatives such as AI2-THOR or Habitat on HM3D for two reasons: first, Matterport3D consists of real photographic scans, providing the visual fidelity required for DINOv2 features to generalize reliably to unseen scenes; second, its discrete graph-based navigation abstracts away low-level motor control, allowing us to focus exclusively on the high-level spatial reasoning problem of where to search next.

5.2 Data Generation & Training

To train ProReFF f we use a subset of the Matterport3D [?] dataset, comprising 20 buildings for training and 6 for validation. For the test of the search agent, we use 20 separate buildings. For each panoramic viewpoint, we encode its 18 RGB images with a pre-trained feature extractor, DINOv2 [?], obtaining L2-normalized patch embeddings of shape $H \times W \times E$ per image, with $H = W = 37$. We resize the corresponding depth images to the same spatial resolution and reconstruct a pointcloud in the local coordinate frame of the viewpoint center, assigning each 3D point its corresponding embedding. This process is performed once across all 26 buildings which comprise ~ 3000 viewpoints, and the result is stored. At training time, given a viewpoint, we sample $N = 200$ points $\{\mathbf{p}_i\}_{i=1}^N \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ with corresponding embeddings $\{\mathbf{q}_i\}_{i=1}^N \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and construct training triplets:

$$\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{v}_{ij}, \mathbf{q}_j) \mid i, j \in \{1, \dots, N\}\}, \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{ij} = \mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$, yielding N^2 training triplets per viewpoint. We then minimize \mathcal{L} as defined in ?? over all triplets. To improve generalization, we augment the training data by applying a small random Gaussian spatial perturbation to \mathbf{v} and a full random rotation, encouraging the alignment network to learn a robust canonical frame rather than overfitting to the specific geometry of the training scenes.

5.3 Human Experiment Platform

To establish a human baseline for comparison with ProReFF and the other agents, we developed a platform in which human participants were tasked with finding target objects in unknown indoor environments using the Matterport3D Simulator [?]. An example of the interface is shown in ??.

Figure 8: Simulator window during the execution of a challenge by a human. The user has to find a kettle (top left) and they can either look around with WASD or teleport to a different viewpoint in the current view by pressing on of the numbers shown at screen, i.e. pressing 3 will teleport the user in front of the armchair on the left.

Participants navigate the environment using keyboard commands: pressing a number key teleports the participant to the corresponding neighboring viewpoint rendered on screen, while WASD keys control the camera orientation. Before beginning the experiment, participants were shown an instruction screen explaining the task and the controls, and were required to complete a set of warmup challenges, not drawn from the 100 evaluation challenges, to become familiar with the interface. An episode terminates under two conditions: either the DINOv2 cosine similarity between the

current observation and the target query embedding exceeds the success threshold τ_{stop} as described in ??, or the participant manually terminates the episode by pressing **p**, either upon believing they have found the object or upon deciding to abandon the search.

6 Experimental Evaluation

We divide the evaluation of our method into two parts. First, we present the predictive capabilities of ProReFF by examining its ability to predict feature neighborhoods in unseen scenes. In the second part, we present the results for the object search agent by comparing it to different baselines in the Matterport simulator.

6.1 Evaluation of Predictive Power

Before deploying our trained ProReFF-model, we examine whether it meaningfully captures feature neighborhoods. We do so by studying its inferences on 6 unseen buildings comprising 730 scenes where each scene is a 360° viewpoint.

Pointwise-based evaluation: First, we build the set of evaluation tuples in the same way as done for training in ???. We then compute the cosine similarity between \mathbf{q} (GT) embeddings and \mathbf{q}' (predicted) embeddings for unseen scenes. The results are shown in ???. The model trained with the Alignment Network achieves higher similarity compared to the basic predictor (*base*), but shows decreased performance when alignment is not employed during inference (*aligned original*), as the model learned to predict embeddings in a canonical frame defined by the alignment network. We present a qualitative result in ??, in which we selected one validation scene, picked one image embedding, and passed it to both predictors, along with the 3D positions relative to the query. We then plotted the pointwise similarity between GT and predictions for the *base* predictor (trained without alignment) (a)

Figure 9: Distribution of pointwise cosine similarities between ground truth and predicted embeddings. *base*: predictor trained without Alignment Network. *aligned*: predictor trained with Alignment Network, tested with positions rotated into canonical frame. *aligned original*: same *aligned* model tested with unrotated scene positions, showing frame-dependency of the learned predictions.

and the *aligned* predictor (b), and showed what the *aligned* predictor sees after the Alignment Network rotates the input points (c). However, such point-wise predictions cannot estimate whether the network captured a meaningful distribution of a feature’s semantic neighborhood.

Clustering-based evaluation: For each validation scene, we sample a query position and extract its embedding $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^E$ from the scene. To ensure meaningful and diverse queries (avoiding featureless surfaces like walls), we compute the mean embedding of the scene and sample randomly from embeddings in the top 20% most dissimilar to the mean. We then extract ground truth embeddings $\{\mathbf{e}_i\}_{i=1}^N$ from all 3D points within a 3-meter radius of the query position. We cluster these embeddings into K clusters using K -means, obtaining the ground truth clustering:

$$\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, \dots, c_K\},$$

where each c_k is a cluster such that $\sum_{k=1}^K |c_k| = N$.

Figure 10: Qualitative impression of similarity difference of predicted features given base model (a) and aligned model (b). Taking a query embedding from a validation scene and querying the model for embeddings of all other points, we observe a stark difference in the semantic accuracy of the predictions. We visualize this here as a heat map (blue = similar, red = dissimilar). In (c), we visualize the impact the rotation predicted by the Alignment Network has on the scene.

To obtain predicted embeddings, we pass \mathbf{q} to ProReFF along with the relative positions \mathbf{v}_i corresponding to the ground truth points. The model returns per-point mean predictions $\boldsymbol{\mu}'_i$ via $(\boldsymbol{\mu}'_i, \hat{\sigma}'_i) = f_\theta(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{v}_i)$. We cluster the predicted means into K clusters to obtain the predicted clustering:

$$\mathcal{C}' = \{c'_1, \dots, c'_K\}.$$

For each cluster k with centroid $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$ and member embeddings $\{\mathbf{e}_i\}_{i \in c_k}$, we compute the angular standard deviation:

$$\sigma_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|c_k|} \sum_{i \in c_k} (\cos^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_k^\top \mathbf{e}_i))^2}$$

To compare \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}' , we find the optimal cluster correspondence π^* using the Hungarian algorithm with angular centroid distances as costs. We then compute this metric, inspired by the Wasserstein distance adapted for ℓ_2 -normalized embeddings:

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}') = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \cos^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_k \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}'_{\pi^*(k)}) + \left| \sigma_k - \sigma'_{\pi^*(k)} \right|$$

This captures both centroid alignment (first term) and spread consistency (second term). Lower values indicate better preservation of the semantic distribution structure.

Baselines: We compare our models against two baselines: (1) *random*, which generates random unit vectors, and (2) *mean*, which predicts solely the mean embedding of the ground truth scene for each of the scene embeddings. All embeddings are then clustered.

Results: We evaluate four model configurations with $K = 10$ clusters, shown in ???. We fix $K = 10$ as it reflects the typical number of semantically distinct regions visible in a 360° indoor viewpoint. The predictor trained with the Alignment Network (*aligned*) achieves a substantially lower distance than the basic predictor

Figure 11: Cluster-based distance between ground truth and predicted embedding distributions. Lower values indicate better preservation of semantic structure. *base*: predictor without alignment. *Aligned*: predictor with Alignment Network using rotated input positions. *Aligned original*: same model using unrotated scene positions. *Aligned sphere*: same model with uniformly sampled spherical positions. **Baselines**: *random* (random embeddings) and *mean* (all embeddings set to scene mean).

(*base*) trained without alignment and significantly outperforms both baselines. The *base* model performs similarly to the *mean* baseline, suggesting it suffers from mode collapse, predicting a narrow range of embeddings describing the scene in general but lacking semantic diversity. Notably, the *aligned* model shows consistent performance whether using: (a) original scene points rotated by the Alignment Network (*aligned*), or (b) points uniformly sampled on a 3-meter sphere matching the size of the ground truth sample (*aligned sphere*). This demonstrates that the model successfully generalizes beyond the training distribution and can predict semantic neighborhoods from arbitrary spatial queries without requiring the alignment network during inference. Given this result, we can now query the model for feature neighborhoods close to a query embedding in a specified radius r . This makes a general prediction, directly applicable to spatial-semantic search tasks without requiring scene-specific calibration.

To further illustrate the effect of the Alignment Network on the predicted distribution we fit a UMAP projection [?] to the ground truth embeddings of the scene and apply the same learned projection to the predicted embeddings, ensuring that

Figure 12: UMAP visualization of ground truth clusters embeddings (left), *base* model predictions (center), and *aligned* model predictions (right). Cluster centroids are marked as circled points. The *base* model exhibits severe mode collapse, whereas the *aligned* model retains substantially more of the semantic diversity around the query embedding. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the Alignment Network at resolving conflicts in the training data.

both sets are embedded in the same low-dimensional space and are therefore directly comparable. To assign semantic labels to the predicted embeddings, we cluster both the ground truth and predicted embeddings into $K = 10$ clusters. For each predicted cluster centroid, we compute its cosine similarity to all ground truth cluster centroids and assign the label of the most similar ground truth centroid, allowing a direct visual comparison of the semantic structure captured by each model. The UMAP visualization is illustrated in ???. The *base* model exhibits severe mode collapse, predicting a narrow cluster of embeddings, while the *aligned* model recovers a distribution that more faithfully reflects the semantic diversity of the ground truth neighborhood, both in the number of matched centroids (9 vs. 4 for *base*) and in the spread of the clusters.

6.2 Object Search

We perform our evaluation on the Matterport3D simulator [?], which provides a navigation graph for agent movement. Using this graph allows us to focus on the

effectiveness of search strategies while minimizing confounding factors from low-level movement or collision dynamics that arise in continuous physics-based environments such as HM3D [?] or RoboTHOR [?].

Experimental Setup: We select 20 buildings (B), not belonging to the model’s training set, from the Matterport3D dataset, which comprise mainly large multi-floor houses, and defined 23 target objects (O) (e.g. cup, bed, kettle...) to search for. Each building is composed of a set of scene viewpoints (S), connected by the Matterport3D simulator’s navigation graph. We define a challenge as the tuple $c = (b, s, o)$, where $b \in B$ is a building, $s \in S$ is the starting scene, and $o \in O$ is the text identifying the target object. For each building b we crafted 5 challenges by selecting 5 different starting scenes and 5 target objects such that object diversity is maximized across the same building. To ensure that each target object is present in its assigned building, we used object labels from the Matterport3D annotations and further verified them manually, yielding 100 challenges in total.

All agents operate in the Matterport3D simulator and have access to the full connectivity graph of the building as well as perfect 6-DoF poses at every step. At each step, an agent receives an RGB image and a depth image. Using the depth image and the known pose, each depth observation is unprojected into 3D space and merged into a building-level point cloud that accumulates across steps. Each 3D point is assigned a VLM embedding (DINOv2 or CLIP) extracted from the corresponding RGB patch, producing an incrementally growing semantic point cloud. Agents use this shared representation to reason about the environment. Navigation actions are discrete: the agent can either rotate in place or move to a neighbouring viewpoint in the connectivity graph. The agent is given a budget of $T = 100$ steps, where only moves between viewpoints count as a step, rotations do not. A challenge is deemed a success if the agent reaches a labeled goal viewpoint or if the cosine similarity between the agent’s current observation embedding and the target query embedding exceeds a threshold $\tau_{stop} = 0.55$, and a failure otherwise. Labeled goal viewpoints

are defined as the viewpoints at which human participants manually terminated a successful challenge, after manual verification that the target object was indeed visible from that position. Each time an agent moves to a new unvisited viewpoint, it does a 360° spin. We subdivide the constructed pointcloud into cells of 3 meters side length.

ProReFF for our agent (??) we used the following configuration: number of clusters $K = 10$, threshold when to follow the max similar point to the query $\tau = 0.3$, tolerance $\epsilon = 0.05$, max spatial context expansion level $L = 2$ with radii $r_1 = 0.1$ and $r_2 = 1.0$. We ablate over the choice of τ and share the results of the ablation in ??.

Baselines: We compare against the following baselines:

Query Follower greedily navigates toward the unvisited viewpoint whose current observation embedding is most similar to the target query, without any predictive model. We deploy this strategy using both CLIP and DINOv2 features.

Random chooses any unvisited viewpoint to navigate to.

BFS and *DFS* perform blind breadth-first and depth-first traversal of the connectivity graph respectively, using the query embedding only to detect success, serving as uninformed search baselines.

CLIP on Wheels (CoW) [?] uses CLIP as an encoder and scores each frontier point by computing the similarity between the scene point embedding and the query embedding. If the score exceeds a threshold, the agent navigates to the corresponding frontier, otherwise it performs a random exploration step.

Human Baseline: To contextualize agent performance, we collected human navigation data on the same challenges. We collected data from 15 participants, each of whom completed 20 challenges. Participants were shown the same RGB observations available to the agents and instructed to find the target object as efficiently as

Table 1: Object search results on Matterport3D environments ($N=100$ episodes).
SR = Success Rate; SPL = Success weighted by Path Length (higher is better for both).

Method	Overall		Single-Floor		Multi-Floor	
	SR	SPL	SR	SPL	SR	SPL
Random	0.45	0.05	0.6	0.08	0.3	0.03
BFS	0.95	0.25	0.98	0.27	0.92	0.23
DFS	0.90	0.35	0.92	0.41	0.88	0.29
CoW [?]	0.78	0.30	0.80	0.35	0.76	0.24
Query Follower (CLIP)	0.84	0.42	0.94	0.55	0.74	0.30
Query Follower (DINO)	0.86	0.44	0.98	0.55	0.74	0.34
ProReFF (Ours)	0.94	0.53	0.96	0.63	0.92	0.42
Mean	0.82	0.33	0.88	0.41	0.75	0.26
Human Participants ($N = 15$)	0.95	0.66	0.95	0.69	0.96	0.62

possible. The participants never encountered the same environment twice, thereby eliminating learning effects that the agents could not experience.

Evaluation Metrics: To evaluate performance on the challenges, we employ two standard navigation metrics commonly used in the literature [?].

Success Rate (SR): Fraction of challenges in which the agent found the object.

Success weighted by inverse path length (SPL):

$$\text{SPL} = \frac{1}{|C|} \sum_{i=1}^{|C|} S_i \cdot \frac{\ell_i}{\max(p_i, \ell_i)},$$

where ℓ_i denotes the optimal path length to address challenge i , p_i denotes the path length produced by the agent, and S_i indicates binary success.

Results: We present the results of the navigation experiments in ???. The overall average success rate lies at 82%, with an average SPL of 0.33. Upon inspection of the results, we note a difference in agent performance when tasked with searching

for an object located on another floor. We thus also report the performances for the single-floor and multi-floor challenges separately.

Given that success rates are generally high, except for the random agent, we focus primarily on the difference in SPL. While BFS achieves the best overall success, ProReFF achieves a similarly high success while also being twice as efficient. Notably, the *Query Follower* agents also exhibit strong performance. While their success rates are an average of 10 points lower than ProReFF, they do rank second and third in SPL after ProReFF. The CoW agent ranks second lowest on both success rate and SPL. We find this to be the case because it is a mixture of the Random agent and the Query Followers, as it follows embedding similarity only when it exceeds a certain threshold. All agents show a decrease in SPL in the Multi-Floor scenario compared to the single-floor, but ProReFF remains the most robust. We find that having to pass a staircase creates a bottleneck in the navigation heuristic for the less context-aware agents. ProReFF, on the other hand, is able to use the semantic context provided by the learned field to consider the stairwell as a worthwhile exploration direction. The feature fields increase the semantic context, enabling the agent to make informed decisions even in more challenging scenarios, whereas the simple query follower has a smaller, more local semantic context, hence working much better on single-floors. We observe in ?? that the Wasserstein scores assigned to the point cloud effectively guide the agent toward regions near the goal (green-blue), while discarding less promising areas (yellow-red).

Our human evaluation shows that humans can solve the challenges with equal success and efficiency, regardless of whether they are single- or multi-floor. As expected, our participants achieved the highest success and SPL overall, but surprisingly, the SPL was 0.66 on average. Given that they can be considered experts at navigating unfamiliar human environments, we infer that the artificial agents achieve 80% of expert performance on average.

Finally in ?? we show the per-object SPL of all the agents and the human baseline and

Figure 13: We compare Query Follower against the ProReFF agent and show the navigation path of both (pink arrows). Agents start at the blue circle, in the first picture the Query Follower travels to the goal (pink circle) by following cosine similarities to the query which we draw on the pointcloud as a heatmap where blue = similar, red = dissimilar. The second and third pictures show the ProReFF Wasserstein distance scores for the feature field at the second level of context expansion (2, more coarse) and the first level of expansion (1, near the query, so most of the points are very dissimilar).

Table 2: Per-object SPL for all methods. Bold = best among competing methods per row.

Query	n	Random	BFS	DFS	CoW	QF (DINO)	QF (CLIP)	ProReFF (Ours)	Human
bathtub	5	0.09	0.26	0.46	0.42	0.28	0.36	0.55	0.60
bed	5	0.04	0.25	0.34	0.24	0.13	0.28	0.25	0.57
book	5	0.10	0.39	0.07	0.27	0.49	0.34	0.44	0.67
chair	5	0.28	0.45	0.47	0.52	0.50	0.57	0.56	0.81
coffee machine	2	0.03	0.25	0.36	0.15	0.57	0.51	0.63	0.72
cup	4	0.07	0.24	0.36	0.17	0.10	0.27	0.44	0.29
dishwasher	5	0.02	0.10	0.16	0.16	0.41	0.34	0.60	0.76
fireplace	5	0.03	0.21	0.29	0.21	0.67	0.44	0.61	0.72
fruit bowl	4	0.03	0.20	0.37	0.23	0.52	0.32	0.65	0.52
kettle	3	0.05	0.14	0.22	0.17	0.17	0.42	0.52	0.62
nightstand	5	0.01	0.20	0.38	0.43	0.49	0.40	0.50	0.79
oven	5	0.00	0.21	0.24	0.22	0.38	0.23	0.27	0.64
potted plant	4	0.10	0.15	0.36	0.37	0.50	0.64	0.42	0.71
refrigerator	4	0.03	0.16	0.17	0.32	0.49	0.53	0.60	0.64
shower	5	0.00	0.30	0.51	0.42	0.32	0.52	0.48	0.69
sink	5	0.06	0.35	0.37	0.63	0.82	0.68	0.81	0.75
stove	5	0.02	0.19	0.41	0.22	0.32	0.37	0.76	0.75
teapot	4	0.02	0.15	0.34	0.19	0.53	0.77	0.58	0.58
toaster	1	0.00	0.28	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.07	0.54
towel	5	0.05	0.28	0.62	0.10	0.61	0.41	0.49	0.73
TV	5	0.02	0.22	0.43	0.35	0.53	0.40	0.67	0.61
washing machine	4	0.04	0.32	0.30	0.30	0.53	0.36	0.64	0.51
WC	5	0.02	0.41	0.40	0.34	0.40	0.30	0.48	0.71

in ?? we use the same data but visualize only the SPLs of the Query Follower (DINO), ProReFF and humans as bar plots. ProReFF achieves the best SPL on 15 out of 23 object categories, showing that it is broadly competitive rather than strong on a few outliers. Human participants achieve consistently high SPL across categories, suggesting that spatial common sense remains a frontier for learned agents. We refrain from drawing per-category conclusions beyond this, as the small number of episodes per object ($n \leq 5$) makes individual results unreliable; a systematic per-category analysis would require a larger evaluation set.

We note in our ablation of τ in ??, that this choice is critical for agent performance. As τ decreases, the ProReFF agent’s behavior approaches that of the Query Follower ($\tau = 0$), relying increasingly on direct similarity rather than co-occurrence reasoning. Conversely, increasing τ improves SPL in multi-floor scenarios, suggesting that the learned field helps the agent escape local minima on the current floor. However, setting τ too high degrades single-floor performance, and we found empirically that $\tau = 0.3$ achieves the best overall trade-off.

Figure 14: Per-object SPL for QF (DINO), ProReFF (Ours), and Human across all 23 object categories. Each group of three bars corresponds to one object; objects are ordered alphabetically and split across four rows for readability.

Table 3: Ablation on the threshold parameter τ for ProReFF.

τ	Overall		Single-Floor		Multi-Floor	
	SR	SPL	SR	SPL	SR	SPL
0.20	0.91	0.46	0.96	0.59	0.88	0.34
0.25	0.91	0.48	0.96	0.60	0.86	0.35
0.30	0.94	0.53	0.96	0.63	0.92	0.42
0.35	0.92	0.47	0.96	0.49	0.88	0.45

7 Summary

This thesis addressed the problem of object search in previously unseen indoor environments. Efficiently finding a target object requires an agent to reason about where objects are likely to reside relative to the surrounding scene, even when the target is not yet visible. This capacity, commonly referred to as object co-occurrence reasoning, is a prior that humans acquire implicitly through experience but that remains difficult to endow robotic agents with in a general, open-vocabulary manner.

Existing approaches to this problem fall into two broad categories. Methods based on classical co-occurrence statistics or learned semantic maps represent objects as discrete categorical labels, limiting their ability to generalise to novel object categories without re-annotation and re-training. More recent methods leverage Large Language Models or vision-language similarity to enable open-vocabulary search, but remain dependent on discrete object proposals from an external detector, or are limited to scoring exploration directions based solely on what is currently visible, with no mechanism to reason about what might lie beyond the current frontier.

To address these limitations, we introduced ProReFF (*Probabilistic Relative Feature Fields*), a self-supervised method for learning spatial co-occurrence structure directly from visual feature embeddings, without requiring object labels or semantic annotations. ProReFF is trained on RGB-D observations from the Matterport3D dataset, from which dense semantic point clouds are constructed by assigning DINOv2 patch embeddings to reconstructed 3D points. Given a query embedding and a spatial

offset, ProReFF predicts the distribution of features likely to appear at that relative location, encoding the statistical regularities of how semantic content co-occurs across indoor environments.

A key challenge in training ProReFF is the inherent ambiguity of viewpoint-relative training data: observing the same scene from different positions produces contradictory training signal for the same displacement vector. We addressed this with a learned alignment network that resolves these contradictions during training by predicting a canonical rotation for each training triplet, without requiring any additional supervision.

Building on ProReFF, we presented an object search agent that uses the trained field to guide exploration toward semantically promising regions. At each navigation step, the agent either follows the most similar observed point directly, or queries ProReFF over a sphere of spatial offsets relative to the target embedding to identify scene regions whose semantic content best matches the predicted feature neighborhood. The agent operates at multiple spatial scales, expanding its context when no sufficiently informative match is found at the current scale.

Before deploying ProReFF as a navigation agent, we evaluated its intrinsic predictive capabilities on unseen buildings from the Matterport3D dataset. We assessed the model both pointwise, by measuring the cosine similarity between predicted and ground truth embeddings, and at the distribution level, by comparing the semantic clustering structure of predicted and ground truth feature neighborhoods using an angular Wasserstein distance metric. The latter evaluation measures whether the model captures the full diversity of semantic content that tends to appear around a query embedding, rather than collapsing to a single average prediction. Our results demonstrated that the model trained with the alignment network substantially outperforms a model trained without it on both metrics, and significantly outperforms random and mean embedding baselines. Notably, the aligned model generalises to feature neighborhoods sampled on a uniform sphere, confirming that it learns a gen-

eral notion of spatial co-occurrence structure rather than overfitting to the specific geometry of training viewpoints.

We evaluated ProReFF on 100 object search challenges across 20 unseen buildings from the Matterport3D dataset, comparing against several baselines including frontier-based methods, vision-language similarity agents, and human participants. ProReFF achieved a success rate of 0.94 and an SPL of 0.53, outperforming all automated baselines on both metrics. The improvement was most pronounced in multi-floor scenarios, where ProReFF achieved an SPL of 0.42 compared to 0.34 for the strongest baseline, demonstrating that the learned spatial context enables more robust reasoning in challenging configurations where simpler methods struggle. Human participants achieved an SPL of 0.66, providing an upper bound against which ProReFF attains approximately 80% of expert performance.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we presented ProReFF, a self-supervised method for training a probabilistic predictor of spatial feature co-occurrences on pre-trained visual features. Different from object-centric methods, ProReFF does not require explicit object labels, but can be trained directly from RGB-D observations. We also proposed a navigation agent that exploits these relative feature fields to enable open-vocabulary object search. In our evaluation, we studied the capacity of ProReFF to learn meaningful co-occurrences of features in natural indoor scenes and demonstrated especially the utility of the learned data decomposition introduced into the training process. We showed that the model trained with this decomposition can infer a diverse feature neighborhood that matches the ground truth feature distribution. In evaluating our navigation agent against other baselines on 100 navigation challenges in the Matterport3D environment, and contrasting its performance with that of human participants, we established an upper bound on expected agent performance. Measured by this bound, our ProReFF agent achieves 80% of human performance.

Limitations. Several limitations of the current work merit discussion. First, the agent relies on perfect 6-DoF poses provided by the simulator and on a precomputed navigation graph. Deploying ProReFF on a real robot would require replacing these with a SLAM pipeline and a continuous motion planner, introducing noise in both localization and depth unprojection that could degrade the quality of the accumulated semantic point cloud. Second, the exploitation threshold τ has a notable impact

on agent performance, as shown in our ablation, and its optimal value appears to be environment-dependent. In our evaluation, τ was fixed across all buildings; an adaptive mechanism for estimating this threshold from the current scene distribution could improve robustness. Third, the current multi-scale expansion strategy relies on manually chosen radii; a learned or adaptive scale selection mechanism would be a natural extension. Finally, while the discrete graph-based evaluation allows clean comparison of search strategies, it abstracts away the challenges of real-world deployment, including partial observability, sensor noise, and dynamic environments.

Future Work. Our evaluations have also raised questions that require further inquiry. Two of our baselines, which simply follow feature similarities, perform quite competitively with our more informed agent in single-floor settings. This raises the question of how much spatial co-occurrence information is already implicitly encoded in the feature spaces of VLMs such as DINOv2 and CLIP. We suspect that these implicit priors are limited to the local visual context and cannot capture the full 3D spatial structure of multi-floor environments. A systematic study of how feature similarity degrades with physical distance could clarify when an explicit co-occurrence model such as ProReFF is necessary and when a simpler similarity-based strategy is sufficient.

A natural extension of the agent would be to also predict the semantic content beyond each frontier from the currently observed scene context, allowing the agent to reason about unobserved space from both directions simultaneously. From a deployment perspective, combining ProReFF with an active mapping strategy that maintains an explicit uncertainty map over unexplored regions would allow the agent to balance co-occurrence priors against new observations. Evaluating such a system on continuous physics-based environments such as HM3D [?] and, ultimately, on a real robotic platform would allow us to assess the practical utility of co-occurrence-based reasoning under the full complexity of real-world deployment.

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